

Thermal Synthesis of Norgirinimbine and its Linear Isomer : A New Synthesis of Girinimbine

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First synthesis of linear pyranocarbazole ring system (11) and the thermal synthesis of norgirinimbine (13) have been reported. Antimony trichloride has been reported as a decarboxylating agent.

SINCE the discovery of the pyranocarbazole ring system in girinimbine (1) in 1964 by Chakraborty *et al.*¹, there has been numerous reports of naturally occurring alkaloids with such a ring system or its variants^{2,3}. The synthesis of girinimbine by various workers^{4,5} provided the first synthesis of such a pyranocarbazole ring system. The essential feature of all those syntheses was the introduction of a C₆-fragment into a phenolic carbazole unit, *i.e.* 2-hydroxy-3-methyl carbazole (2). Recent report of the structure of pyranquinone-A (3) and pyranquinone (4) from *Murrava euchrestifolia* by Furukawa *et al.*⁶ and their synthesis prompted us to report here our previously unpublished work^{7,8} on the thermal synthesis of norgirinimbine (13), its linear pyranocarbazole isomer (11) and a synthesis of girinimbine (1). Our method of synthesis of the linear pyranocarbazole skeleton differ from that of the synthesis of pyranocarbazoloquinone reported by Furukawa *et al.*⁶.

2-Hydroxycarbazole-3-carboxylic acid (5) and β , β -dimethylacrylic acid (6) being heated at 145° in presence of SbCl₃ was *in situ* decarboxylated to 2-hydroxycarbazole which then gave rise to linear (7) and angular (8) chromanones oxygenated at 2-position. This gave us a method for facile decarboxylation process which was used in our previous work in decarboxylation of mukoeic acid⁹ with SbCl₃. On the separation of the chromanone mixture, the linear indolochromanone (7), C₁₇H₁₅NO₂ (M⁺ 265), m.p. 212-15°; λ_{max} 236, 244, 277, 288, 327 nm (log ϵ 4.40, 4.29, 4.55, 4.40, 4.09) was obtained as a major product. The spectral curve had the similarity with 3-formylcarbazole. The compound on treatment with sodium borohydride in methanol yielded a colourless alcohol (9), C₁₇H₁₇NO₂ (M⁺ 267), m.p. 223°; λ_{max} 237, 262, 300 nm (log ϵ 4.55, 4.55, 4.23 and 4.0). The tosyl derivative of 10, m.p. 155°, on subsequent dehydro-sylation in collidine furnished the linear pyranocarbazole derivative (11), C₁₇H₁₅NO (M⁺ 249), m.p. 170°; λ_{max} 234, 260, 298, 328 nm (log ϵ 4.50, 4.65, 4.07, 3.8). The mass spectral fragmentation showed a high intensity mass spectral

peak at *m/s* 234 showing the presence of the carbazol o-pyrillium ion.

The pale yellow indolochromanone (8), C₁₇H₁₅NO₂ (M⁺ 265), m.p. 165°; λ_{max} 228, 283, 298 nm (log ϵ 4.65, 4.23). The uv spectra had the shape of the curve strikingly similar to that of 1-formylcarbazole suggesting it to be the angular chromanone. The compound 8 on borohydride reduction furnished an alcohol (12), C₁₇H₁₇NO₂ (M⁺ 267), m.p. 150°; ν_{max} 1 670 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} 237, 252, 281, 303 nm (log ϵ 4.58, 4.23, 4.02, 4.09). The alcohol (12) on dehydro-sylation via its tosyl derivatives in boiling collidine furnished norgirinimbine (13), C₁₇H₁₅NO (M⁺ 249), m.p. 185°; λ_{max} 223, 236, 283, 328 nm (log ϵ 4.45, 4.67, 4.65, 4.0), which was very similar to girinimbine (1), showing it to be angularpyranocarbazole structure. The angular chromanone structure was also established by a separate experiment leading to a new synthesis of girinimbine.

The acyl derivative (14) obtained by acylating 2-hydroxycarbazole-3-carboxylic acid (5) with β , β -dimethylacryloyl chloride on Fries rearrangement in presence of AlCl₃ in nitrobenzene furnished the chromanone (15), which on methylation with diazomethane furnished the methyl ester (16). Decarboxylation of 15 with SbCl₃ at 145° furnished the chromanone (8). The chromanone (16) on reduction with borohydride furnished the alcohol (17) C₁₉H₁₉NO₄, m.p. 167°, which on dehydro-sylation as above via its tosyl derivative (18) furnished 3-carbomethoxy pyranocarbazole, (19) C₁₉H₁₇NO₃, m.p. 200°. This compound (19) on reduction with LiAlH₄ for 8 h furnished girinimbine (1), C₁₈H₁₇NO (M⁺ 263), m.p. 176°; λ_{max} 224, 238, 288, 330 nm (log ϵ 4.59, 4.70, 4.65, 4.04).

The synthesis of linear pyranocarbazole isomer of norgirinimbine provides the first synthesis of linear pyranocarbazole ring system not previously reported so far from natural sources or otherwise.

Reagents: (i) β,β -dimethylacrylic acid, SbCl_3 , 145° , (ii) NaBH_4 reduction, (iii) 9 (R=H), 10 (R=Ts); tosylation, dehydrotosylation, (iv) NaBH_4 reduction, (v) tosylation, dehydrotosylation, (vi) β,β -dimethylacryloyl chloride, (vii) CH_3N_2 , NaBH_4 reduction, (viii) tosylation dehydrotosylation, (ix) LiAlH_4 reduction

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were dried over P_2O_5 at a temperature 78° before analysis.

The indolochromanones (7) and (8): 2-Hydroxy-carbazole-3-carboxylic acid (464 mg) and β,β -dimethylacrylic acid (210 mg) were mixed and heated in presence of SbCl_3 . The reaction mixture was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with 5% HCl and made acid free. On removal of the solvent an oily product was obtained which was chromatographed over neutral alumina. The benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) eluent on evaporation gave a solid residue which on recrystallisation from a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene furnished compound 7, m.p. 212° (Found: C, 76.64; H, 5.50; N, 5.42. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$ calcd for: C, 76.96; H, 5.70; N, 5.28%); $R_f = 0.37$ in chloroform-ethyl acetate (3:1). The benzene-chloroform (1:1) eluent on evaporation gave a solid residue which on recrystallisation from benzene gave compound 8, m.p. 161° (Found: C, 77.20, H, 5.96; N, 5.70. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$ calcd.

for: C, 76.96; H, 5.70; N, 5.18%); $R_f = 0.4$ in benzene-chloroform (1:1).

The alcohol (9): The indolochromanone (7) in dry methanol (5 ml) was reduced with sodium borohydride (10 mg) at $0-5^\circ$ for 12 h. After removal of methanol, the residue was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . On working up the reaction product an oily residue was left, which on crystallisation from benzene and chloroform yielded 9, m.p. 223° (Found: C, 76.20; H, 6.08; N, 5.80. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for: C, 76.38; H, 6.41; N, 5.24%); $R_f = 0.45$ in 20% methanolic benzene.

The linear isomer of norgirinimbine (11): The compound 9 (30 mg) on treatment with *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride in pyridine and subsequent work up furnished the tosyl derivative (10), which on recrystallisation from benzene melted at 155° . The tosyl derivative in β -collidine (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 h at $100-20^\circ$. The reaction product was poured into crushed ice to yield a solid precipitate which was chromatographed over alumina. The solid obtained from petroleum ether furnished 11, m.p. 170° (Found: C, 82.16; H, 6.20; N, 5.93. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$ calcd. for: C, 81.90; H, 6.06; N, 5.62%).

The alcohol (12): The indolochromanone (8; 30 mg) on reduction with sodium borohydride in methanol (10 ml) by the procedure mentioned for 9 furnished the alcohol (12), m.p. 167° (homogeneous to tlc) (Found: C, 76.68; H, 6.72; N, 5.34. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$ calcd for: C, 76.38; H, 6.41; N, 5.24%).

Norgirinimbine (13): The compound 12 (15 mg) was dehydrotosylated by the process described above via its tosyl derivative using collidine as the solvent to yield 13, m.p. 185° (Found: C, 81.65; H, 6.31; N, 6.82. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$ calcd. for: C, 81.90; H, 6.0; N, 5.62%).

The indolochromanone (15): 2-Hydroxy-carbazole-3-carboxylic acid (2.8 g) in pyridine (6 ml) was acetylated with 2,2-dimethylacryloyl chloride (in 16 ml pyridine) at $0-5^\circ$. Working up the reaction mixture and crystallisation of the solid from alcohol, yielded the acetylated product (14; 75%), m.p. 147° (homogeneous to tlc; yield 75%). The compound (1.1 g) on treatment with AlCl_3 in nitrobenzene at $0-5^\circ$ and work up furnished the chromanone (15; 40%), m.p. 238° (Found: C, 70.25; H, 4.67, N, 4.40. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_4$ calcd. for: C, 69.89; H, 4.89; N, 4.53%). The compound 15 on decarboxylation with SbCl_3 at 145° furnished the chromanone (8) (m.p., m.m.p., uv, ir identical).

The alcohol (17): Chromanone (15; 200 mg) in methanol (25 ml) was methylated with diazomethane and on working up (homogeneous to tlc) yielded solid 16, m.p. 200° (Found: C, 70.78; H, 5.58; N, 4.38. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4$ calcd. for: C, 70.53; H, 5.30; N, 4.33%); λ_{max} 227, 277 and 283 mm. The chromanone methyl ester in dry

methanol (15 ml) was reduced by addition of sodium borohydride. On work up, a solid obtained was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether mixture to yield 17, m.p. 167° (homogeneous to tlc) (Found: C, 70.38; H, 6.15; N, 4.42. $C_{19}H_{19}NO_4$ calcd. for: C, 70.14; H, 5.89; N, 4.30%); λ_{max} 237, 252, 281 and 303 nm.

The pyranocarbazole 19: The alcohol (35 mg) in dry benzene (3 ml) was tosylated with *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride (15 mg in 1 ml pyridine) in the usual way. The tosyl derivative (18) after crystallisation from benzene was dehydrotosylated in a solution of β -collidine (3 ml) by refluxing for 6 h. On work up and crystallisation of the crude solid, the pyranocarbazole (19) was obtained (Found: C, 74.48; H, 5.62; N, 4.78. $C_{19}H_{17}NO_8$ calcd. for: C, 74.25; H, 5.58; N, 4.56%).

Girinimbine (1): A solution of 19 (35 mg) in dry THF (10 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (40 mg) in dry THF.

The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h and then refluxed for 8 h. On work up and recrystallisation of the reaction product from benzene solid 1 (homogeneous to tlc) was obtained (25%), m.p. 176° (Found: C, 82.31; H, 6.72; N, 5.28. $C_{18}H_{17}NO$ calcd. for: C, 82.10; H, 6.51; N, 5.32%).

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